

CHROMATOGRAPHIC STUDY OF ANIONIC COMPLEXES. PART V. SEPARATION OF IONS IN PRESENCE OF TARTRATE USING METHANOL AS SOLVENT

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Attempts to separate Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and Fe^{3+} in mixtures by filter paper strip chromatography have been made, using tartrate as complexing agent and aqueous methanol as solvent. The effect of adding varying concentrations of the complexing agent to the solution has been studied. The R_L and R_T values have been determined in each case. In general, good separation of ions occurs when total metal to tartrate ratio is below 1:1; with higher concentrations of tartrate, separation is not possible. The R_L and R_T values change with the concentration of ion, and therefore their use in qualitative analysis may be regarded to be limited. But, nevertheless, we have observed that it is possible to separate the ions and detect them on filter paper qualitatively after separation. The figures show clearly the sequence of separation of the ions though the R_T values of the ion at the top merges into the R_T of the ion separating out next. These results therefore qualitatively show that the complex-forming property of the ions may be useful in the separation of these ions from mixtures.

In a number of previous publications, we have described our studies on the diffusion of various metal ions through filter paper strips in the presence of varying concentrations of different complexing agents, using aqueous alcohol as solvent (Singh and Dey, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1958, 159, 290, 332; 1959, 165, 81, 179; *J. Chromatog.*, 1959, 2, 95; 1960, 3, 146; *Proc. Nat. Acad. Sci., India*, 1959, 28A, 43, 87).

In the present communication we have extended the studies to separations using aqueous methanol as solvent and recorded only some of the typical observations out of a very large number of experiments.

EXPERIMENTAL

Standard solutions of sodium tartrate, cupric sulphate, cobalt sulphate, nickel sulphate, ferric sulphate and cadmium chloride were prepared, using reagent grade chemicals. The method adopted was the strip filter paper chromatographic technique, using an arrangement described by Gage, Douglass and Wender (*J. Chem. Ed.*, 1950, 27, 159). Various concentrations of methanol were tried and 50% methanol was found suitable as a solvent for the separations. A series of mixtures containing equal concentrations of metal solutions with varying proportions of sodium tartrate were prepared, keeping the total volume constant. The ratio of the total concentration of the metals (obtained by adding the concentrations in molarity of the metals) to the concentration of tartrate added is expressed as the metal: tartrate ratio (equivalents of tartrate). The mixtures were spotted on filter paper strips, prepared from Whatman filter paper No. 1. The chromatograms were run at a constant temperature in a room, with temperature controlled at 30°, and the time allowed was 1.5 hours for diffusion,

In order to ascertain whether a good separation is taking place in mixtures or whether overlapping is occurring between two ions, R_L and R_T values instead of R_f values are often useful (Majumdar and Chakrabarty, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 1957, 17, 415). So we have determined these values and considered them.

For the economy of space, the experimental tables have been omitted and figures showing the variation of the R -values with the concentration of tartrate employed in some typical cases have only been reported.

Separation of Cu^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and Fe^{3+}

The final concentration of each of the metal ions was 0.042 M and a mixture of H_2S -water and $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ solution was used for developing. The results are plotted in Fig. 1. The separation of Cd^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Fe^{3+} ions is possible when 0.234 to 0.60 equivalents of tartrate are used. When the ratio of metal : concentration of tartrate is 1 : 0.7 to 1 : 0.9, the Fe^{3+} ions are found to diffuse into those of copper (II). With a ratio 1 : 1 to 1 : 1.6, there is only a separation of the Cd^{2+} ions, and with higher concentrations

FIG. 1

of the same, separation is not possible. It was noted that the R_L values of Cd^{2+} do not change appreciably with the additions of tartrate. The R_L values of Cu^{2+} do not change with small additions of tartrate, but gradually decrease with higher concentrations of the same. The R_L values of Fe^{3+} initially decreased with the addition of tartrate, but afterwards they tended to become constant. The R_T value of Fe^{3+} became constant with higher concentrations of the complexing agent.

Separation of Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Fe^{3+}

The final concentration of each of the metal ions was 0.042 M and a mixture of dimethylglyoxime and $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ solutions was used for developing. The separation

of Ni^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Fe^{2+} ions (Fig. 2) is possible up to the addition of 1.17 equivalents of tartrate. With higher concentrations of the same, separation is not possible. A good separation was obtained when 0.313 to 0.6 equivalents of tartrate were used. It was noted that the R_L values of Ni^{2+} did not change with small additions of tartrate but

FIG. 2

decreased slightly with higher concentrations of the complexing agent. The R_L values of Cu^{2+} decreased slightly with the additions of the complexing agent. The R_L and R_T values of Fe^{2+} behave in a similar manner as in Fig. 1.

Separation of Cu^{2+} , Co^{2+} and Fe^{2+}

The final concentration of each of the metal ions was 0.042M and a mixture of H_2S -water and $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ solution was used for developing. The separation of Co^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Fe^{2+} (Fig. 3) is possible up to the addition of 0.70 equivalents of complexing

FIG. 3

agent. With increase in the concentrations of the same, no separation is possible. A good separation was obtained when 0.156 to 0.6 equivalents of the complexing agent were added. It was noted that the R_L values of Co^{2+} and Fe^{3+} decreased slightly with the additions of the complexing agent and finally tended to become constant with higher concentrations of tartrate ions. The R_T value of Fe^{3+} became constant with 0.47 equivalents of the complexing agent.

Separation of Fe^{3+} , Co^{2+} and Cd^{2+}

The final concentration of each of the metal ions was 0.042M and a mixture of H_2S -water and $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ solution was used for developing. The separation of Co^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and Fe^{3+} ions (Fig. 4) was effected up to the addition of one equivalent of tartrate. With higher concentrations of the same, no separation was possible. A good separation was obtained when 0.078 to 0.766 equivalents of the complexing agent were added. It was seen that the R_L values of Co^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and Fe^{3+} did not change with small addition of the complexing agent, but by increasing the concentration of the same, the values decreased and finally became constant. The R_T values of Co^{2+} and Cd^{2+} became constant with 0.39 equivalents of the complexing agent.

FIG. 4

Separation of Cu^{2+} , Cd^{2+} and Co^{2+}

The final concentration of each of the metal ions was 0.042M and a mixture of H_2S -water and $\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ solution was used for developing. No precipitate was obtained in the beginning up to 0.234 equivalents of tartrate added, but with higher concentrations of the same, precipitation occurred. When 1.2 or more equivalents of the tartrate were added, dissolution of the precipitate took place. The separation of

Co²⁺, Cd²⁺ and Cu²⁺ ions (Fig. 5) was effected up to 0.77 equivalents of tartrate added. A good separation was obtained when 0.234 to 0.53 equivalents of the complexing agent were added. It was seen that the R_L values of Co²⁺ and Cd²⁺ did not change with small additions of the complexing agent. These values gradually decreased with the increase

FIG. 5

in the concentration of the complexing agent and had a tendency to become constant when large proportions of the same were employed. The R_T values of Cd²⁺ and Cu²⁺ became constant with 0.47 and 0.53 equivalents of the complexing agent respectively.

Separation of Fe²⁺, Cu²⁺, Cd²⁺ and Co²⁺

The final concentration of each of the metal ions was 0.031M and a mixture of H₂S-water and K₄Fe(CN)₆ solution was used for developing. A typical table of separation is shown below.

TABLE I

No.	Ratio of total metal : Tart ²⁻	Cobalt (II).		Cadmium (II).		Copper (II).		Iron (III).	
		R _L	R _T						
1	1 : 0.00	0.95	0.93	0.93	0.91	0.91	0.84	0.84	0.00
2	1 : 0.05	0.95	0.93	0.93	0.90	0.90	0.80	0.80	0.00
3	1 : 0.10	0.94	0.92	0.92	0.89	0.89	0.79	0.79	0.00
4	1 : 0.15	0.94	0.92	0.92	0.89	0.89	0.80	0.80	0.00
5	1 : 0.25	0.94	0.92	0.92	0.89	0.88	0.80	0.80	0.25
6	1 : 0.30	0.94	0.92	0.92	0.88	0.88	0.80	0.80	0.33
7	1 : 0.35	0.94	0.92	0.92	0.88	0.88	0.81	0.80	0.37
8	1 : 0.40	0.94	0.92	0.92	0.88	0.88	0.81	0.80	0.40
9	1 : 0.45	0.94	0.91	0.92	0.88	0.87	0.80	0.80	0.42
10	1 : 0.50	0.94	0.91	0.91	0.87	0.87	0.80	0.80	0.47
11	1 : 0.55	0.94	0.91	0.91	0.85	0.85	0.79	0.79	0.51
12	1 : 0.60	0.94	0.91	0.91	0.85	0.85	0.79	0.79	0.54
13	1 : 0.65	0.94	0.91	0.91	0.84	0.84	0.78	0.78	0.57

The separation of Co^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Cu^{2+} and Fe^{2+} ions is possible up to 0.8 equivalents of tartrate added. With higher concentrations, no separation occurs.

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